

Short name	Public awareness of CCUS	Long name	Public awareness and knowledge of CCUS – magnitude, gaps, and variation
Geographical scope	Most research on public perceptions of CCUS focuses on research in European nations (either single countries or comparative) ¹⁻² . North American and East Asian nations are also regularly represented in the research literature.		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Numerous studies have assessed level of public awareness and specific knowledge about CCUS ²⁻⁴ ; knowledge and awareness vary cross-nationally, and regionally within countries as well (places with more exposure to industrial projects or government discourse and planning show higher knowledge) ⁵⁻⁶ . Nevertheless, across virtually all studies to date, the common finding is that public understanding of CCUS is quite limited ²⁻⁴ . Even if people have heard of it, they know little about it. Over the last two decades of public perceptions research knowledge and awareness are climbing, but slowly ^{2,5,7-8} .		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	This lack of knowledge could be seen as beneficial for governments or industries seeking to expand deployment of CCUS. If people are poorly informed about a new technology, then this is seen in social-psychology as an object to which public attitudes would generally be malleable ⁹ . There might be potential for further information, and targeted communication, to influence level of support and acceptance. Social scientific research on CCUS repeatedly champions the need for effective communication on this topic – indeed, identifying messages, messengers, visuals, dissemination pathways, and specific language that will lead to higher public acceptance of CCUS is the primary purpose of many such studies ¹⁰ .		
Other issues this affects	Public support for CCUS, public engagement with CCUS, cross-national variations in CCUS attitudes and beliefs		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upham, P., & Roberts, T. (2011). Public perceptions of CCS: emergent themes in pan-European focus groups and implications for communications. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 5(5), 1359-1367. • Tsvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. <i>Heliyon</i>, 5(12), e02845. • Seigo, S., Dohle, S., & Siegrist, M. (2014). Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): A review. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i>, 38, 848-863. • Witte, K. (2021). Social acceptance of carbon capture and storage (CCS) from industrial applications. <i>Sustainability</i>, 13(21), 12278. • Whitmarsh, L., Xenias, D., & Jones, C. R. (2019). Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. <i>Palgrave Communications</i>, 5(1). 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021). How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 81, 102236. • Gough, C., Taylor, I., & Shackley, S. (2002). Burying carbon under the sea: an initial exploration of public opinions. <i>Energy & Environment</i>, 13(6), 883-900. • Shackley, S., Gough, C., & McLachlan, C. (2005). The public perceptions of carbon dioxide capture and storage in the UK. In <i>Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies 7</i> (pp. 1699-1704). Elsevier Science Ltd. • Heberlein, T. A. (2012). <i>Navigating environmental attitudes</i>. Oxford University Press. • Otto, D., & Gross, M. (2021). Stuck on coal and persuasion? A critical review of carbon capture and storage communication. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 82, 102306.
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[2] Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon*, 5(12), e02845.

[3] Seigo, S., Dohle, S., & Siegrist, M. (2014). Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 38, 848-863.

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[10] Otto, D., & Gross, M. (2021). Stuck on coal and persuasion? A critical review of carbon capture and storage communication. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 82, 102306.